
Milestone M-JIP2-10 (M-A2. COHESIVE.4.6)

Workpackage JIP2-WP4 Data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control

Responsible Partner: BfR

Contributing partners: IZS-AM, FHI/NIPH, IZSLER, FLI, FOHM/PHA, NVI

GENERAL INFORMATION

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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	Milestone M-JIP2-10 (M-A2. COHESIVE.4.6) Prototype for tracing framework ready
WP and Task	JIP-WP4: Data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control; T2: Development of a platform-independent tracing framework ST2: Programming a software and developing an algorithm
Leader	BfR
Other contributors	IZS-AM, FHI/NIPH, IZSLER, FLI, FOHM/PHA, NVI
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Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	DEC
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PROTOTYPE FOR TRACING FRAMEWORK READY

Birgit Lewicki, Marion Gottschald, Marco Rügen, Alexander Falenski, Annemarie Käsbohrer, Armin Weiser

In subtask 2, several modules for data collection, cleaning, visualisation and reporting – in part developed in the framework of other projects - will be unified in one platform:

- A data collection module
- An interactive analysis module
- A WGS-data integration module
- A reporting module
- A synchronization module with the desktop version of FoodChain-Lab (FCL)

The interactive analysis module including the algorithm to analyze delivery networks was developed in the framework of another European project and is now integrated in the tracing portal.

A first demonstrator of a reporting module – the Rapid Outbreak Assessment (ROA) style – was implemented and integrated in the tracing web portal. The ROA style visualises tracing, sample and case information in a format which is suitable for publishing the results of tracing analyses in outbreak reports such as the EFSA-ECDC Joint Rapid Outbreak Assessments just in one click. For this, a JSON-based data exchange module was developed to import delivery data obtained from EFSA.

A prototype of a data cleaning module was developed as a KNIME server workflow. This module will be implemented in the FCL tracing web portal soon.

A prototype of an online data collection mask for tracing data was developed in the framework of a national project but is not yet integrated in the tracing web portal. The mask is available in multiple languages: German, English, Italian and Norwegian. Currently, a task and user management feature is being developed in the national project which will be integrated into the tracing portal as well.

During summer 2019, a web-security audit of the tracing web portal was conducted in the framework of another European project to ensure secure handling of sensitive information.

A first implementation of the tracing web portal including an interactive analysis module, a reporting module and a synchronization module with the desktop version of FoodChain-Lab is available in a test environment. The production system of the tracing portal is currently being set up. It is already accessible at <https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin> and will be switched to production mode in early 2020. More modules will be integrated in 2020.